

[研究文章 Research Article]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20698979>**New Records of *Macrosiagon bifasciata* (Marseul, 1877) (Coleoptera: Ripiphoridae) from the Oriental Region**FANG-SHUO HU^{1,*}, BIN-HONG HO², YUN HSIAO³

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Abstract: *Macrosiagon bifasciata* (Marseul, 1877) is a widespread species in the eastern Palaearctic and Oriental regions. We report this species from Borneo (Malaysia), Luzon (Philippines), and Taiwan for the first time. The status of a similar species, *M. bipunctata* (Fabricius, 1801), from Taiwan is discussed, as it is likely a misidentification of *M. bifasciata*.

Key words: New faunistic records, distribution, Taiwan, Malaysia, Borneo, Philippines, Luzon

Introduction

Ripiphoridae is a parasitoid beetle family with over 400 species described worldwide and hosts including Blattodea, Hymenoptera, and Coleoptera (Lawrence et al., 2010). The genus *Macrosiagon* is among the most species-rich in the family, with over 200 species-group names described (Batelka, 2011). This genus is an exclusive parasitoid of Hymenoptera (e.g., Batelka & Hoehn, 2007; Hu & Lo, 2020). *Macrosiagon bifasciata* (Marseul, 1877) is a widespread species in the eastern Palaearctic and Oriental regions (see the distribution section in Results for details) (Batelka, 2004, 2007, 2011; Yoshitake & Batelka, 2018). In the present paper, we provide new records of *M. bifasciata* from the Oriental region, specifically Borneo (Malaysia), Luzon (Philippines), and Taiwan, which fill in distributional gaps for this species.

Materials and methods

The specimens used in this study are deposited at the following collections:

FSHC — Fang-Shuo Hu's collection, Yilan, Taiwan (F.-S. Hu);

BHHC — Bin-Hong Ho's collection, Taipei, Taiwan (B.-H. Ho);

CWLC — Chen-Wei Lee's collection, Taichung, Taiwan (C.-W. Lee);

NMNS — National Museum of Natural Science, Taichung, Taiwan (B.-C. Lai & J.-F. Tsai);

SYSU — Museum of Biology, School of Life Sciences, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China (H. Pang).

Photos were taken with a Canon EOS 850D camera and a Canon MP-E65 f/2.8 1–5x macro lens, stacked using Helicon Focus 8 software, and subsequently edited in Adobe Photoshop 2025. Specimens were identified by comparison with authoritatively identified specimens at SYSU and the literature of Batelka (2007) and Yoshitake & Batelka (2018). Labels are quoted verbatim. The English translation for Chinese labels is provided in brackets.

Results and discussion***Macrosiagon bifasciata* (Marseul, 1877)**

(Fig. 1)

Material examined. **MALAYSIA:** 1♂ 1♀, Borneo, Sabah, Keningau, Mt. Trus Madi, 17.VIII.2023, B.H. Ho lgt. (BHHC); 1♀, same locality as the previous one, ca. 1200 m, 04-VIII-2023, leg. F. S. Hu by light trap (FSHC). **PHILIPPINES:** 1♀, Luzon Papi, Gawa-an, Balbalan; 17°30'40.4"N, 121°12'35.91"E, (970~1025m) VIII/7---8/2019, J. F. Tsai & H. Y. Tseng & R. C. Cheng, Light trap & at night & day time (NMNS). **TAIWAN:** 1♀, New Taipei City, Wulai Dist., Wulai vil. (烏來里), Huanshan Rd. (環山路), alt. 215 m, 24.860705N 121.549144E, 1.VII.2023, F.S. Hu, B.H. Ho, D. Král, J. Růžička lgt. (FSHC); Taichung City: 1♀, III.30.2026, 桐林生態廊道 [=Tonglin Ecological Corridor], 24.04800° N, 120.78408° E, Chen Wei Lee leg. (CWLC).

Compared specimens. CHINA: 1♂, Guangdong, Ruyuan, Luoyang Commune (乳源洛陽公社), Liaoche (廖城), 24.V.1974, det. J. Batelka, 2014 (SYSU En-095816); 1♀, Jiangxi, Shangrao (上饒), Sanqingshan (三清山), 13–18.VIII.2006, H.D. Chen lgt. (SYSU En-001066).

Figure 1. Habitus of *Macrosiagon bifasciata* (Marseul, 1877) in dorsal view: A. male (Borneo), B. female (Taiwan).

Distribution. *Macrosiagon bifasciata* has been recorded from Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku, Kyushu, and Ryukyus), China (Beijing, Fujian, Sichuan, and Yunnan), India (Darjeeling, Himachal Pradesh, and Uttar Pradesh), Indonesia (Java and Sumatra), South Korea, Laos (Huaphanh), Nepal (Buri Gandaki), the Philippines (Negros), and Vietnam (Sa pa) (Batelka, 2004, 2007, 2011; Yoshitake & Batelka, 2018). We report it for the first time from Borneo (Malaysia), Luzon (Philippines), and Taiwan.

Remarks. Iwata (1939) reported a similar species, *M. bipunctata* (Fabricius, 1801), from Taiwan. However, voucher specimens have not been available for subsequent studies (e.g., Yoshitake & Batelka, 2018). This species has a wide distribution ranging from the Indian subcontinent, Sri Lanka, Nepal, and Pakistan westward to Senegal (Batelka, 2011), and its distribution range likely extends towards the east of the Indian subcontinent (Batelka, 2007). Taiwan is therefore outside its known natural range. *Macrosiagon bipunctata* can be distinguished from *M. bifasciata* by the second metatarsomere being short and robust, shorter than the third tarsomere. The specimens we examined have the second metatarsomere as long as the third tarsomere, which is consistent with *M. bifasciata*. Given our discovery of *M. bifasciata* in Taiwan, it is more likely that Iwata's (1939) record was based on a misidentification.

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東方區之雙帶巨噬蜂大花蚤（鞘翅目：大花蚤科）新紀錄

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摘要: 雙帶巨噬蜂大花蚤 (*Macrosiagon bifasciata*) 是古北區東部與東方區的廣布種，我們首次報導產自婆羅洲（馬來西亞）、呂宋島（菲律賓）與臺灣的標本，並討論其近似種雙點巨噬蜂大花蚤 (*M. bipunctatum*) 於臺灣的紀錄，推測該紀錄為雙帶巨噬蜂大花蚤的錯誤鑑定。

關鍵詞: 新動物相紀錄、分布、臺灣、馬來西亞、婆羅洲、菲律賓、呂宋島